

Fateha Aziz
PhD candidate, University of Worcester
fateha.aziz@yahoo.com
Abstract for Symposium on the Life and Work of Terry Pratchett, Dublin City University
31st March 2016

A Metamodern Reading of Terry Pratchett's Johnny Maxwell Trilogy (1992-1996)

This paper analyses Terry Pratchett's Johnny Maxwell trilogy (1992-1996) using a new cultural paradigm, metamodernism. Metamodernism is a structure of feeling which oscillates between a postmodern scepticism and a modern optimism for sense, meaning, and direction. It is a generational response of the millennials of their experience during late 20th and early 21st centuries, a period shaped by contemporary geopolitical, financial, and environmental problems¹. While postmodernism deconstructs, metamodernism moves between poles of "present, past and future; mindsets and systems"², reconstructing these into new narratives for new conflicts and circumstances. This paper recognises that the Johnny Maxwell trilogy is consistent with the metamodern structure of feeling as proposed by Timotheus Vermeulen and Robin van den Akker via three elements namely, conflicts, subjectivity shifts, and power. In the trilogy, Johnny realise that he lacks the tools for solving the conflicts that he encounters due to the collapse of grand narratives around him. Adopting the metamodern attitude, his process of problem solving involves constructive engagement and storytelling. He picks and chooses narratives that work then reconstructs them into solutions, actively participating in improving the condition of his social domain, a process that results in shifts in subjectivity and affects the domain's power landscape. From this analysis, this paper argues that a metamodern reading of the trilogy forms a literary

¹ Vermeulen, Timotheus, and Robin van den Akker. "Notes on Metamodernism." *Journal of Aesthetics and Culture*. (2) 2010. Web. 14 Aug. 2014.

² Potter, Cher. "Timotheus Vermeulen Talks To Cher Potter." *TANK*. Web. 22 Aug. 2014.

representation of the millennial experience and construction of childhood in the socio-cultural context of late 20th and early 21st centuries.

Brief bio:

Fateha is currently writing her doctoral thesis, a metamodern reading of Terry Pratchett's corpus of children's fiction at the University of Worcester, UK under the supervision of Professor Jean Webb. Her other research interests include literary representation of the grotesque and portrayal of grief in children's literature. She can be reached at twitter.com/ffateha_